

Analysis of the composition of dust in the atmospheric air of the city.
Makhmudov Rustam Zayniddinovich.

Tashkent University of Information Technologies, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

rustammaxm@gmail.com

+998933542025

Abstract: This paper analyzes the level of air pollution in the city of Tashkent, with a focus on the annual dynamics of pollutant emissions from stationary sources and the concentration of particulate matter PM_{10} and $PM_{2.5}$. In particular, the study examines the permissible concentration limits of these particles and their impact on human health. Key pollution sources such as industrial enterprises and motor vehicles are discussed, along with climatic factors that affect the dispersion and transformation of pollutants. The research shows that monitoring the levels of $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} is critically important for ensuring environmental safety and public health. The findings indicate the need for the implementation of modern air purification technologies to reduce pollution levels.

Keywords: $PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , air pollution, sanitary and hygienic standards, stationary sources, emission dynamics, public health, filtration systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

Currently, our country applies sanitary and hygienic standards, such as the maximum permissible concentrations (MPC) of microorganisms in the atmospheric air of populated areas in the Republic of Uzbekistan. These standards, which came into effect on May 12, 2004, serve as the main criteria for assessing air pollution levels and protecting public health, establishing MPCs for pollutants in the atmospheric air in mg/m^3 . Special standards also exist for particulate matter less than 10 micrometers (PM_{10}) and less than 2.5 micrometers ($PM_{2.5}$), aimed at protecting health and improving air quality [3,6].

Such regulations have been implemented in numerous countries over a significant period of time and are supported by comprehensive monitoring and research as well as the development of methods to improve the effectiveness of air pollution control measures. The World Health Organization (WHO) highlights the

importance of fine particulate matter (PM) for hygiene and its impact on human health.

These particles, which have an aerodynamic diameter of less than 10 micrometers (PM₁₀) or 2.5 micrometers (PM_{2.5}), can remain suspended in air for extended periods, travel long distances, and enter the lungs deeply, bypassing natural defenses and posing a significant risk to health. Therefore, it is crucial to monitor their concentrations in urban air. Regular monitoring of these particles helps prevent the development of chronic illnesses and improves the overall quality of life of the population. Advanced filtration methods and air purification systems play a critical role in reducing harmful particle concentrations in the environment. Investing in these technologies and encouraging their use is a crucial step towards improving environmental conditions and protecting public health.

2 Statement of the problem

The level of air pollution in a large megacity is determined by emissions of harmful substances from both stationary and mobile sources. The total volume of pollutant emissions into the atmosphere of Tashkent averages 550 thousand tons per year. The dynamics of emissions from stationary sources and transportation are presented in Table 1.

According to the wind rose, Tashkent is most frequently ventilated by winds from the southwest (21%) and west (23%) directions throughout the year.

In Table 2, data on climate characteristics are presented.

Table 1. Dynamics of pollutant emissions from stationary sources into the atmosphere of Tashkent over 5 years.

Years	Stationary Sources (thousand tons)	Solid Particles (thousand tons)	Mobile Sources (thousand tons)	Solid Particles (thousand tons)
2016	560,0	2,8	475,0	1,0
2017	570,0	2,9	480,0	1,0
2018	580,0	3,0	485,0	1,1
2019	590,0	3,0	490,0	1,1
2020	600,0	3,1	495,0	1,2

Table 2. Characteristics of climatic conditions

Years	Precipitation (number of days)	Wind Speed (m/s)	Wind Frequency (%)	Winds with Speed 0-1 m/s (%)	Fog Frequency (%)
2016	116	1.3	7,6	35,0	0,5
2017	112	1.2	7,7	35,5	0,5
2018	97	1.3	7,8	36,0	0,5
2019	113	1.3	7,9	36,2	0,5
2020	113	1.3	8,0	36,5	0,6

The state of air pollution depends not only on the quantity and chemical composition of emissions but also on climatic conditions that influence the transport, dispersion, and transformation of the emitted substances. Tashkent has climatic conditions that generally contribute to a somewhat higher level of air pollution by harmful substances compared to other cities. The location of Tashkent and its urban planning create favorable conditions for the dispersion of harmful substances in the atmosphere, which helps to reduce the level of air pollution compared to other cities in Uzbekistan. However, despite these factors, the level of pollution in Tashkent remains above the permissible standards, especially during periods of increased dustiness, such as in spring and summer [4,6].

The annual average concentration of suspended particles in the atmospheric air of Tashkent varies within the range of 0.2 to 0.8 MAC (maximum allowable concentrations). Throughout the year, the average monthly concentrations typically range from 0.5 to 1.2 MAC. Figure 1 illustrates the annual trend of average monthly MAC for the years 2023 and 2022 [1].

Table 3. Monthly Changes in PM_{2.5} Concentration in 2022-2023

Month	2022 Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	2023 Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)	Exceeded 60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (2022)	Exceeded 60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (2023)
January	143.2	92.0	Yes	Yes
February	117.3	106.5	Yes	Yes
March	73.8	66.5	Yes	Yes
April	52.9	44.5	No	No
May	52.4	42.9	No	No
June	46.4	43.8	No	No
July	39.8	50.0	No	No
August	42.2	38.9	No	No
September	53.8	46.0	No	No
October	125.9	70.4	Yes	Yes
November	251.0	196.8	Yes	Yes
December	197.5	204.2	Yes	Yes

Fig. 1. Annual Variation of Average Monthly Maximum Permissible Concentrations (MPC)

In the spring months, dustiness increases due to the melting of snow cover and drying of the soil. The values of maximum concentrations across all city areas range from 1.2 to 2.4 MAC on average, while the frequency of exceeding the MAC fluctuates on average from 0.2 to 2.5%. Overall, air pollution in the city is most often assessed as elevated in December, June, August, and October [3,6].

Research shows that particles sized between 2.5 and 10 micrometers pose the greatest threat to human health. Fine particles, such as PM₁₀, enter the atmosphere directly through emissions from construction sites and industrial enterprises. The main sources of these particles are stationary facilities, such as power plants, oil and gas processing plants, waste incineration plants, as well as transport, trains, ships, and airplanes [3, 4].

During technological processes, a significant amount of dust and harmful gases is released into the air, which noticeably increases overall atmospheric pollution. Therefore, it is necessary to implement modern technologies and filtration systems to reduce the impact of these sources on the environment [1, 2].

Fig. 2. Integral mass distribution curves of particles by equivalent diameters in a probabilistic-logarithmic grid for a dust sample collected in a residential area on the street.

An analysis of the particle size distribution of emissions from enterprises that significantly contribute to pollution has been conducted. Figures 2-6 present integral mass distribution curves by particle diameters from emissions of waste incineration furnaces, vehicles, trains, and airplanes.

$D(d), \%$ — this axis (the vertical axis) indicates the percentage content of PM_{10} particles in the distribution. The graph shows the total share of each particle fraction in the set. For example, the value $D(d) = 50\%$ means that 50% of PM_{10} particles have a diameter less than or equal to the specified size.

$d_p, \mu m$ — this axis (the horizontal axis) shows the size (diameter) of PM_{10} particles in micrometers (μm). PM_{10} particles are those in the air that can have a diameter of up to 10 micrometers. In this graph, sizes are presented in the range from $0.1 \mu m$ to $100 \mu m$.

Fig. 3. Integral mass distribution curves by particle diameters $D(\delta p)$ in a probabilistic-logarithmic coordinate grid for dust sampled from the atmosphere.

Fig. 4. Integral mass distribution curves by particle diameter ($D\delta p$) in a logarithmic-probabilistic coordinate grid: 1 - in zone; 2 - in zone; 3 - in zone.

Fig 5: Integral mass distribution curves for particles with different diameters in a logarithmic scale for dust sampled from a rotary kiln used for waste incineration.

The analysis of the obtained data showed that the industrial dust has a polydisperse composition and consists of finely dispersed and medium-dispersed fractions with sizes up to 20 microns. These particles can penetrate the lungs when inhaled and remain there. The average concentration of fine dust in emissions from the studied industries is presented in Table 3.

Table 3.

Average content of fine dust

Location	D(D δ p) PM ₁₀ , %	D(δ p) PM _{2.5} , %
Tashkent	35.5	31
Bukhara	55	11.3
Samarkand	34.1	10.9

2.1 Mathematical model

An analysis of the content of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ particles in the atmospheric air of a megacity was carried out. Determining the concentration of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ particles is more technically challenging than determining the overall concentration of suspended solids, as it requires isolating fractions with dust content up to 2.5 micrometers and 10 micrometers from the total mass of solid particles in atmospheric air [11, 12]. A sufficient amount of data must be processed to ensure a homogeneous sample of results. Establishing the uniformity of the data involves statistical analysis in the following steps [13]:

1. The arithmetic mean concentration value of C (mg/m³) is calculated using the formula:
2. The standard deviation of the concentration values is calculated:
3. The coefficient of variation is calculated:

$$R_{cp} = \frac{R_1 + R_2 + \dots + R_n}{n} \quad (1)$$

where $R_1, R_2 \dots R_n$ — are the results of the measurements of the concentrations of suspended substances, n — is the number of measurements.

б) the standard deviation of the measurement results is calculated.

$$\lambda = \sqrt{\frac{(R_{cp} - R_1)^2 + (R_{cp} - R_2)^2 + \dots + (R_{cp} - R_n)^2}{n - 1}} \quad (2)$$

and his assessment

$$\gamma_c = \frac{\lambda}{\sqrt{n}} \quad (3)$$

с) there is a confidence interval

$$\varepsilon = \gamma_c t \quad (4)$$

where t — is the student's coefficient, the value of which is determined at a confidence probability $P = 0,95$ depending on the number of degrees of freedom

$$k = n - 1;$$

The student's coefficient (Student's t-coefficient) is a special coefficient used in statistical analysis to assess distributions. It is applied to calculate the confidence interval of the mean based on small samples

2.2 Source data (Description of datasets)

The student's coefficient is used in the following cases: To determine the confidence interval, that is, to estimate the range of deviation of the data from the total value. It is used for small samples (usually if the sample size is less than 30). It is used to calculate the confidence interval for random variables with unknown variance or normal distribution. The Student coefficient value is usually given in statistical Tables and depends on the sample size (n) and the confidence level (P). In this case, the degree of freedom is selected ($k = n - 1$). For example, if the confidence level is $P = 0.95$ and $k = 10$, the value of t is taken from the table below.

Practical application

The Student's coefficient is used in confidence interval formulas as a multiplier, for example:

$$\bar{X} \pm t \cdot \frac{s}{\sqrt{n}}$$

Where: — average value, — Student coefficient, s — standard deviation of the sample, n — sample size. This formula helps to determine the confidence interval for the average value, and the value of t is taken from the student's coefficient table.

The results of definitions for which the inequality is performed are excluded from the sample

$$|\bar{C} - C_1| > \varphi. \quad (5)$$

If less than 30% of the measurement results are excluded from the sample, the average concentration value can be used as the value C . However, if more than 30% are excluded, it may be necessary to re-check the uniformity of the remaining data to ensure its reliability.

If fewer than three measurements are left after excluding unsuitable results, it would be beneficial to perform additional measurements to obtain more data. This would help to accurately determine the concentration and ensure compliance with established standards by assuming the maximum single concentration value.

$$C_{\max} = \bar{C} + \varphi \quad (6)$$

Fig. 6. Distribution of PM₁₀ particles in the air by posts in 2022.

In contrast to the traditional method, in which an environmental engineer pre-determines fixed measurement points that remain static over extended periods, the proposed approach employs a dynamic forecasting model to predict pollution levels across the entire area. This innovative strategy harnesses advanced predictive analytics to identify potential pollution hotspots and assess variations in air quality over time, allowing for a more proactive monitoring framework.

Leveraging these comprehensive predictions, a Decision Support System (DSS) is utilized to flexibly select measurement locations that are precisely aligned with specific monitoring objectives and the unique priorities of the client. This adaptive approach not only accelerates the response to real-time environmental changes but also enables a more accurate and nuanced assessment of air quality, ensuring that monitoring efforts are both timely and relevant.

Moreover, the DSS integrates a multitude of critical factors, including current weather conditions, existing levels of pollution, and the significance of various geographic areas. This multifaceted analysis empowers decision-makers to choose measurement locations with enhanced precision and operational efficiency. By

capitalizing on these insights, the monitoring process becomes significantly more responsive and strategically aligned with the overarching goals of environmental management and public health protection.

In summary, this modernized approach to environmental monitoring not only substantially enhances the quality of data collected but also fosters more informed decision-making in tackling the complex challenges associated with air quality management. By prioritizing adaptability and precision, this innovative methodology stands to significantly contribute to healthier urban environments and more effective public health strategies.

Conclusion:

1. It is crucial to monitor the levels of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ air pollution to assess the quality of the atmosphere in Uzbekistan. Sanitary and hygienic standards are in place to track these tiny particles, which can be harmful to human health when they enter the lungs through the respiratory system.

2. The primary sources of pollution in Tashkent include particles emitted by vehicles and factories, which can remain suspended in the air for extended periods and travel long distances.

3. Urban planning and natural factors, such as winds blowing from the southwest and west, can contribute to improving air quality in Tashkent.

4. The spring season is marked by a rise in the concentration of soil particles in the air, resulting in elevated levels of air pollution. The peak levels of pollution are typically observed in December and during the months of June, August, and October.

5. The presence of various harmful pollutants, including PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, particularly those originating from industrial sources and vehicle emissions, can have a detrimental impact on human respiratory health.

6. It is essential to adopt advanced technologies to reduce pollutant emissions. This can be accomplished through the implementation of state-of-the-art filtration systems and techniques.

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